

Original Article

COMMUNITY EDUCATION FOR ENHANCEMENT OF PHYSICAL RESOURCES IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to determine the extent to which community education is relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state. One research question and one null hypothesis guided the study. The population of the study comprised of 454 adult learners from 28 adult literacy centers in Enugu state which are 241 female and 213 male adult learners. The population size is manageable as a result of which sampling was not done. The instrument for data collection was the researcher's structured questionnaire that was face validated by three experts. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. Number of questionnaires administered was 454 by the researcher with the aid of two research assistants that were briefed on the content of the questionnaire and the mode of administration to ensure proper administer of the questionnaires. 449 questionnaires were retrieved from the respondents within interval of one month of which 5 copies were not retrieved by some respondents for some reasons best known to them data was analyzed using mean (X) with Standard Deviation (SD) to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Findings among others shows that to a high extent, community education was relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state. Also based on the findings, the researcher recommended among others that the contents of adult education programmes be reviewed to accommodate wide areas that would meet the varying needs of community among others.

Keyword: Community education, enhancement of human livelihood.

Original Article

Introduction

Education is a process of developing human knowledge and skills necessary for individuals, community and national development as well as sustainable growth. It entails the development of physical, mental, moral, social and critical resources capacities for sustainable standard of living. In a broad sense, education is any act or experience that has a formative effect on the mind, character or physical ability of an individual. According to Amos and Madison (2015), the knowledge and skills acquired through education enhances access to critical resources for increased productivity, reduction of social disparities improvement in health conditions, poverty alleviation and the better quality of life. Okafor and Ayo (2023), define education as an affective instrument for harnessing. Human capital and other livelihood for individual, community and national development. It can be asserted that education is one of the most important tools for improving the quality of life and standard of living of the people. Hence, a process by which the society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another for sustainable living standard (Tigelaar and Sins, 2021).

The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) states that education is meant for the acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper value orientation for the survival of the individual and society, the development of the intellectual capacity of the individual to understand and appreciate the environment, the acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which enable individual is to develop into useful members of the community. The acquisition of this knowledge takes various forms such as formal, informal and non-formal. The formal education model that is structured and administered through a rigid curriculum as regards to objectives contains and methodology (Auwal and Jesutofunmi

2023) this type of education is institutionalized, chronically graded and hierarchically structured, spanning lower primary school to the upper reaches of the university. Informal education on the other hand or deliberate.

The acquisition of knowledge in informal education through several life experiences and interactions with the members of the communities. It is a less structured and organized type of learning than formal (Auwal and Jesutofunmi (2023) reported that this type of education could take place at home, in the work place, in the local community and daily life. Non formal education is a more flexible, learner-centered, conceptualized and participatory approach of learning for those who may not attend the rudimentary system of education. It usually takes place in community based settings, workplaces and through the activities of governmental and non-governmental organizations. Hussein (2023) opines that the objectives of non-formal education is to equip the adult with everything he needs for life in order to be relevant to the society by helping to solve some of its problem. This explaining the idea of enhancing the livelihood of the community with no specific target group, non-formal education is structured to accommodate both youths and adults for their transformation and empowerment. It provides individuals or members of the community with necessary knowledge and skills for accessing and utilizing the livelihood at their disposal to improve the quality of life in a given community.

Generally, community is viewed as a group of people living in the same locality with common culture and historical heritage, and is mutually supportive to each other to better their life. Darego Ilomabo (2020) describes community as a group of people that prescribed locality, consisting of constituencies, interest groups and associations with divergent interest, through closely knitted in common goals,

affinity and peaceful coexistence, community draws its range of assets to engage in variety of activities to generate income and meet household needs in pursuance of better living standard. Community education is an aspect of non-formal education and encompasses activities conducted outside the framework of the formal school system to provide selected types of learning and skills acquisition to sub-groups of people in a community. It is an education geared towards encouraging and empowering community members to think about their problems, formulate and embark upon programmes and projects to overcome their challenges (Ihejirika, 2013)

Community education is problem solving centered activity that helps community in building diverse capacities aimed at improving standard using the available resources in their environment. Ukwuaba (2015) posited that community education raises consciousness, promotes understanding and provides the necessary skills as well as human and material resources for social, economic, political and cultural development. Hence, the purpose of community education is to develop the capacity of individuals and groups towards better quality of life. To achieve this transformation, community education incorporates programmes such as adult literacy, extra-moral studies, continuing education of all categories, co-operative society studies, small and medium entrepreneurship, vocational training, health recreational, citizenship education among others. This establishing a direct relationship between community education and livelihood. (Ugwu, 2020).

Livelihood is means of securing the necessities of life. It comprises the capabilities, assets (including both materials and social resources) and activities required for a means of living. In other word, it is the activities, means and entitlement by which individuals make living. Enhancing livelihood therefore seeks to gain an accurate and realistic understanding of people's strengths, social capacity, skills and endowment, and the conversion of the assets into positive lively hood

outcomes (Ahmed Hassan, Kamaruddin and Anuar, 2018).

Livelihood involves proper knowledge of the human, natural, financial and physical requirements to make the best use of the assets to generate income. Livelihood also comprise income in cash and kind, the social relative and institutions that enhance individual and family standard of living and access to social and public service that contribute to the well-being of the individual or family (Ellis, 2013). Means of livelihoods are not the only things that are put into a productive process, but also act as a basic power to act and ultimately bring about changes in society. The five (5) pillars of improving livelihood proposed by sconces as cited by Udoh, Akpan and Uko (2017) include: human, physical, financial, social and natural resources. These resources are relevant in the present study considering their place in the overall improvement of the people.

Human resources represents skills, knowledge, ability to labour and good health that together enable people to pursue different livelihood strategies and achieve their livelihood objectives (Sayer and Campbell 2013). It is the keystone within the sustainable livelihood approach. It relates to a set of human productive capacities that empower the individual or household towards earning livelihood for improved standard of living when utilized (Kamaruddin and Baharuddin, 2015). It comprises the skills, knowledge, ability and good health to pursue different livelihood strategies (Mensah, 2014). Hence the conceived in this study as the totality of individuals capability, knowledge, economy, social and mental ability resulting to the enhancement of livelihood outcome.

Statement of the problem

Despite the several development programmes that exist in Enugu state, poverty rate among the people was 69.2% as at 2018 has reminded increasingly high. This is evident in a poor standard of living, poor health care, reduce life expectancy and unemployment which are prevalent among most

people in the state to cushion this pathetic situation, some programmes of adult education were established by both the government and non-governmental organizations. The essence of these programmes, among other things was to equip the learners with the necessary skills needed to be economically empowered so as to fight the menace brought about by poverty (Omeje, F. U. 2020).

Although instituted adult education programmes provides some skills to community or learners, as the poverty rate continued to escalate among the inhabitants. A fore mentioned programme has not achieved the progressive impact in the lives of citizens to reduce poverty rate. The problem of the study, therefore, was to examine the relevance of community education for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state especially with a view to improving and ensuring sustainable living standards of the citizenry.

Purpose of study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the extent to which community education is relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state:

Research question

The following research questions guided the study:

To what extent is community education relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female adults learners on the extent to which community education is relevant for the human livelihood in Enugu state.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. This design aims at collecting data on and describing in systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population (Nworgu 2015). Or is one in which a group of people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. A descriptive design research is concerned with

specified population of persons, items or situation the way they are. Descriptive survey research design was considered suitable for the study as it solicits for information from the respondents directly and affords all at the respondents equal chance of being chosen for the study. The research was carried out in Enugu state, Nigeria. The choice of Enugu state was as a result of observed high rate of poverty among human livelihood citizens. The population for the study comprised of all 454 female and male adults learners in the twenty eight (28) literacy centers. It was made up of 241 female adult learners and 213 male adult learners. This is based on the data obtained from personnel unit of adult literacy centre (Enugu State No Adult Education Center Monogram, 2022). Sampling was done because the population is manageable.

A structured questionnaire tagged community education for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state developed by the research was used for data collection. The instrument had two sections: A and B. Section A contained the respondents' bio-data while section B has 10 items. The response format for the instrument was a 4-point scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). Each response option had a numerical value assigned to it as follows:

Very High Extent (VHE)	= 4 points
High Extent (VE)	= 3 points
Low Extent (LE)	=2 points
Very Low Extent (VLE)	=1 point

In order to ensure the validity of the instrument, draft copies of the instrument together with the research topics, purpose of the study, research questions, hypothesis and the developed instrument were given to three experts. Two experts were from the department of continuing education and development studies, while the other expert was from the department of mathematics and computer education, all from faculty of education, Enugu state university of science and technology Enugu.

The researcher requested them to assess the adequacy, appropriateness, relevance and clarity of items also instructions to the respondents. The instrument was modified based on the comments of suggestions of the validators. All the items for the purpose of clarity, which the researcher did accordingly. The observations and corrections of the validators guided the production of the final draft that will be used for the study.

To establish the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested using 40 adult learners in five adult literacy centers in Ebonyi state, located outside the area of the study, though they shared similar characteristics with the study area. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's alpha statistical tool to compute the reliability coefficient of each of the clusters of the questionnaire. The researcher with the aid of two research assistants who were briefed on how to administer the questionnaire administered and retrieved the instrument from the adult learners during their classes. The administration and retrieval of completed questionnaire was done within interval of one month to ensure high return

rate. Data was analyzed using the main standard deviation to answer the research questions. The real limit of numbers was used for decision making. This was classified as follows:

Mean scores between 3.50 - 4.00 (Very High Extent) VHE

Mean scores between 2.50 - 3.49 (High Extent) HE

Mean scores between 1.50 - 2.49 (Low Extent) LE

Mean scores between 0.50 - 1.49 (Very Low Extent) VLE

The null hypotheses was tested adopting t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance, where the probability value is less or equal to 0.05 level of significance. The null hypotheses was rejected, but where the probability value is greater than 0.05 level of significance the null hypotheses was not rejected.

Result

Research Question I

To what extent is community education relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state?

Table 1: Mean ratings and standard deviation of respondents on the extent to which community education of human livelihood in Enugu state

S/N	Community education for enhancement of human livelihood	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Good business skills	2.84	0.96	High extent
2	A good knowledge of education (Academic knowledge)	2.59	0.83	High extent
3	A better entrepreneurial skills (Productivity)	2.85	1.22	High extent
4	A good knowledge of good health practices	2.39	8.17	High extent
5	Knowledge of good nutrition	2.64	0.85	High extent
6	Good community skills	2.75	0.89	High extent
7	Ability to maintain good transaction skill with customers	2.65	0.82	High extent
8	Good saving culture	3.09	0.66	High extent
9	Social networking skills (Working together)	2.65	0.80	High extent
10	The will power to achieve goals	2.74	0.85	High extent
Grand mean		2.72	0.87	High extent

The analysis of data presented in Table 1 above shows that all the items except 4 had mean scores of great extent as 2.84, 2.59, 2.85, 2.64, 2.75, 2.65, 3.09, 2.65, and 2.74 respectively with standard deviation scores of 0.96, 0.83, 1.22, 0.85, 0.89, 0.82, 0.66, 0.80 and

0.86 showing the closeness in their responses. The cluster mean of 2.72 and standard deviation (SD) Of 0.87 shows that to a great extent community education is relevant for the enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state.

Hypotheses I

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female adults on the extent to which community education is relevant for human livelihood in Enugu state

Gender	No of Respondents	X	SD of t _{cal}	P _{value}	Decision
Male	302	2.58	0.58 ⁶⁶¹	1.93 _{0.06}	NS
female	361	2.67	0.58		

Table 2 above indicates that at $t = 1.18$ the $P_{value} = 0.24$ at 0.05 level of significance

Since the associated probability value was greater than 0.05 set as benchmark, the null hypothesis is hereby not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female adult learners on the extent to which community education is relevant for the enhancement of livelihood in Enugu state.

Discussion of the findings

Result in research questions shows that community education to high extent was relevant for enhancement of human livelihood in Enugu state. The high recognition is applauded by respondents following the acceptance of null hypothesis. The similar views attested by both male and female respondents established the enormous contributions of community education in enhancing their livelihood. This is also possible considering the various forms community education assumes, while attempting to satisfy the need of learners. Thus, the finding is in tandem with Olori, Peterside and Obama (2019) who revealed that acquisition of income generating skills and health related skills provided through adult education programme has helped the beneficiaries in the achievement of no poverty. Similarly, study by Ekpenyong, Taiwo and Obogua (2018) was reported to align empowered. The empowerment of these learners through non-formal education which community education falls under its preview is believed to serve as a tool for enhancing and sustaining their livelihood.

Recommendations

Table 2: summary of t-test analysis of difference in the mean ratings of respondents on the extent to which community education is relevant for livelihood in Enugu state.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- Organizers of adult education programmers should review the contents of available programmes to accumulate wide areas to meet the varying needs of learners in Enugu state.
- Efforts should be made by facilitators in the teaching of contents relating to protection of environment and its pollution in Enugu state

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